

EASYFRIDGE: THE INFLUENCE ON INCREMENTAL INNOVATION

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10511696

Márcio de Freitas Santa Ana*MSc in Materials Science and Technology, DEPROIN – UERJ, Polo Zona Oeste,
ciedistancia@gmail.com***Neilton Passion de Jesus***Graduating in Production Engineering – DEPROIN – UERJ. West Zone Polo,
neiltonpjj@gmail.com***Letícia Chagas de Araújo***Graduating in Production Engineering – DEPROIN – UERJ. West Zone Polo,
leticiaregina@gmail.com***ABSTRACT**

The present study addresses a challenge common to many homes: the difficulty of moving heavy household appliances, such as refrigerators and washing machines. A product was developed in the form of incremental innovation that incorporates an intelligent lever and a locking system at the base of these appliances, facilitating transport and reducing physical effort for users. The main objective was to improve the user experience, promoting their physical integrity and preserving the devices. The method involved the creation of a customizable product, adaptable to various equipment dimensions. The expected results include a notable reduction in the physical effort required for transportation, preventing potential injuries related to the movement of household appliances. In conclusion, investing in innovative solutions to facilitate the transportation of extremely heavy household appliances not only improves user convenience, but also promotes the long-term health and well-being of consumers, emphasizing the importance of continued technological development in this sector. This innovation represents a significant step towards making domestic activities more efficient, safe and inclusive, thus improving consumers' quality of life.

Keywords: Incremental innovation; mobility; inclusion; security; product development.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the modern scenario, where technological innovation shapes our daily lives, there are opportunities aimed at efficiency and convenience in domestic activities. One of these

challenges is the mobility of large and heavy household appliances, such as refrigerators, stoves and washing machines. The difficulty in moving them not only makes cleaning and maintenance difficult, it also limits flexibility in the design of domestic spaces. This question has intrigued designers and engineers for decades: how can we facilitate the movement of these essential devices without compromising stability and safety in these activities?

In this context, this study proposes an innovative solution to this problem. The central hypothesis is that the integration of a lever and an intelligent locking system acting on the wheels of these household appliances can radically transform the way users interact with this equipment. This study explores not only the challenge of mobility, but also the implications for the efficiency of domestic activities and the quality of life of consumers (SERRANO-GARCÍA, BIKFALVI, et al., 2021).

To answer these questions, this work analyzes the historical evolution of the relationship between design, manufacturing and mobility of household appliances, highlighting the challenges faced by consumers. Furthermore, the socioeconomic context that led to the need for innovations in this field is explored. Through a bibliographic review, different perspectives on innovation in design and product management are discussed, presenting the importance of integration between technology and market demands (ALMODÓVAR, NGUYEN, 2022, HAN, ZHANG, 2021).

By detailing the proposal for an innovative solution, this study offers insights into the practical application of theoretical concepts in the development of household appliance products, examining the design of the solution highlighting its ergonomic and technological characteristics. Additionally, the possible social, economic and environmental impacts of this innovation are analyzed, presenting evidence of how it can not only simplify consumers' daily lives, but contribute to the preservation of the environment and user safety (REIMANN, XIONG, et al. , 2019).

This study aims not only to present a solution in the form of incremental innovation to existing products, but to provoke reflections on the role of design and innovation in transforming everyday challenges into opportunities to significantly improve people's quality of life. By entering this universe of possibilities, this work offers a comprehensive and inspiring vision for future research and developments in the field of product design and development (BOS-BROUWERS, 2010, REIMANN, XIONG, et al., 2019).

Before the Industrial Revolution, designing and manufacturing were intrinsically linked, being essentially the same activity, that is, craftsmanship. In its effort to reduce production costs, the Industrial Revolution separated design as an independent activity. Furthermore, mass

manufacturing processes have imposed a fixed definition of the design process on designers. In fact, in traditional product design, the design process has a very well-defined end point. When a fully defined and manufacturable design proposal is delivered for production, the design process ends and manufacturing begins. Typically, a new design process begins again for the next version of the same product or for a new product that will replace it.

This sequential and linear division between design and manufacturing is a consequence of the mass production principle of the Industrial Revolution. To reduce production time and therefore the cost of the product, dedicated and often expensive tools are required. When these tools are manufactured, the cost of modifying them can be substantial. Therefore, when tool design and manufacturing begins, the design proposal must be “frozen” and the design process ends.

It can be noted that one of the issues that impact the routine activities of a residence is dealing with the mobility of large and heavy appliances such as refrigerators, stoves and washing machines. These heavy objects not only make cleaning more challenging, but also complicate relocation and rearrangement processes within the home environment. Moving an appliance, such as a refrigerator, requires considerable physical effort and, often, external assistance. The lack of mobility of these devices can limit flexibility in the layout of the house, making cleaning and reorganizing spaces difficult. Furthermore, when there is a need to clean behind or under these appliances, the difficulty of the process increases, leading to hard-to-reach areas accumulating dirt and dust over time. This lack of mobility not only consumes time and energy from performers, but can negatively impact the hygiene and comfort of the home environment, highlighting the importance of technological innovations and designs that facilitate the movement of these household appliances.

Innovations that add green technology have received continuous attention from the business sector due to growing concern about the state of the environment (Abdullah, Zailani, Iranmanesh and Jayaraman, 2016). In fact, it is essential that manufacturing companies, especially highly polluting industrial companies, take responsibility for protecting the environment. In addition to the benefits of adjusting their processes to protect the environment, companies must also consider customer needs and corporate social responsibility (Woo, Chung, Chun, Han, and Lee, 2014).

The project aims to fill a critical gap in the market by solving mobility issues associated with large household equipment. The problematic gap is the lack of effective solutions to facilitate the movement of these devices. This not only reduces the need for physical strength, it also makes it easier to thoroughly clean the device and the space where it is located. Currently,

householders face significant challenges when trying to clean inaccessible areas around refrigerators, stoves and washing machines due to their lack of mobility or suitable tools. These difficulties not only affect the cleanliness of your home, they also cost you valuable time and energy. The project aims to fill this gap by offering an innovative solution that not only makes moving these appliances easier, but also simplifies cleaning tasks, making them more efficient and accessible for everyone.

In certain respects, pollution can be seen as evidence of inefficient use of resources (Chen, 2008), which affects company profits. New technology has been credited with solving environmental problems by mitigating the effects of pollutants (Jaffe, Newell, and Stavins, 2005). In this sense, green innovation has been considered essential to deal with environmental issues (Kong, Feng and Ye, 2016).

Environmental sustainability is imperative and offers an opportunity to improve competitiveness using a win-win logic (Porter & Van der Linde, 1995), with companies that pioneer green innovation strategies potentially achieving and maintaining competitive advantages (Albort-Morant, Leal-Millán and Cepeda-Carrión, 2016). According to Rekik and Bergeron (2017), implementing green practices is beneficial for small and medium-sized businesses in terms of financial performance and environmental performance.

In traditional product design, the goal is to create long-lasting items that keep up with changing trends and fashions. However, if design is not fixed, but is always changing just like in our society – there is no such thing as great or perfect: each design is situated in a specific context at a particular time. However, for this scenario to become real, there are issues and challenges to be addressed related to the economic model, marketing strategy, management of updates and improvements, product validation and certification.

This innovative product aims to change the way large household appliances are handled, providing an efficient solution to the mobility challenges they face. By developing external equipment specifically designed to facilitate the movement of these heavy devices, our goal is to drastically reduce the physical force required to mobilize them. This revolutionary product will be equipped with advanced technology such as smooth lifting and sliding systems, providing effortless mobility. In addition to simplifying the relocation of household appliances, the main focus is to facilitate deep cleaning of the home environment. With this product, those responsible for the home will be able to easily move refrigerators, stoves and washing machines to clean difficult-to-reach areas, thus ensuring thorough and complete cleaning. By optimizing the mobility of these equipment, our goal is not only to make household tasks easier, but also

to improve the quality of life, providing a clean and healthy environment in a more efficient and accessible way.

The challenge is not easy, since each dimension mentioned above has its own particularities that will need to be considered from a complete perspective, in order to integrate the parts and achieve positive and permanent results. Therefore, the focus of this study is on identifying ways to promote innovation of meaning in design management through the proposal of an incremental innovation for a household appliance.

The separation between design and manufacturing during the Industrial Revolution was explored, highlighting the need for innovations to overcome mobility challenges in homes. Next, the current scenario of design innovation was analyzed, discussing approaches driven by necessity and technology. The innovative proposal to facilitate the mobility of household appliances was detailed, presenting a practical solution with an intelligent lever and a locking system on the wheels. The conclusion recapped the findings, highlighting the study's relevance to consumers' everyday lives and suggesting opportunities for future research, focusing on practical testing of the innovation and environmentally friendly materials. This division allowed for an in-depth analysis of the problem, proposing an innovative solution based on contemporary design and innovation theories, aiming to improve consumers' quality of life.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Product Design

Design represents the application of human creativity in the creation of products, services, buildings, organizations and environments that meet people's needs, making it an essential activity for sustaining business. Design management, in turn, encompasses a series of activities that aim to implement products, processes or services, incorporating the company's identity, objectives and values. In addition to day-to-day administrative tasks, design management plays a key role in identifying and communicating how design can contribute to a company's strategic value. This involves diagnosis, coordination, negotiation and design activities, which occur both in external consultancies and within the organization, interacting with different sectors such as production, financial planning and marketing. This integration of design into the corporate structure provides a competitive advantage, becoming a core competence that is difficult for competitors to imitate (GATTI JUNIOR, YU, 2017, MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015, SILVA, DACORSO, 2013).

By developing a design mindset within the company, it creates a path for design to become a new core competency, allowing you to visualize the strategy, obtain consensus and commitment from employees, as well as strengthen the brand image, foster loyalty and explore new business opportunities. As for the levels of design management, they represent the different ways of integrating design into the company to assist in the development of strategies. These structural levels include operational, functional and strategic, each playing a crucial role in the effective management of design within the organization (NOGAMI, VELOSO, 2017, SANCHES, MACHADO, 2014).

Many companies underestimate the strategic value of design. They don't realize that design can improve products, environments, corporate communications and identity. In many cases, design activities within companies are limited to the operational level, although many managers recognize that design goes beyond form and usability. Design, in its best scenario, only reaches the tactical level in organizational decisions (CASTRO, 2011, MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015, SANCHES, MACHADO, 2014).

According to experts, design plays a fundamental role in articulating innovation. It is a powerful strategic tool that companies can use to gain a significant competitive advantage. In this context, innovation is not limited to invention; is the ability to transform something invented into something widely used, successfully applying new ideas in practice to create new or improved products, services and processes. Furthermore, innovation is not just creativity, but also the ability to combine ideas in new ways to solve problems and explore novel opportunities. Clarifying these concepts is crucial, as design intentionally incorporates creativity throughout the innovation process, being a key element for successful development (GATTI JUNIOR, YU, 2017, MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015).

It is crucial to understand that innovation in design is not necessarily linked to the creation of something completely new and unprecedented. It may involve finding improved variations on existing ideas, rather than creating something entirely original. This approach is shared by many experts, who recognize the importance of finding new and better variations on already known themes. Design can significantly contribute to the social acceptance of emerging technologies, even if the design itself is not directly linked to their emergence (MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015, MEDEIROS, VIEIRA, et al., 2013, SANCHES , MACHADO, 2014).

Furthermore, it is important to note that many technological innovations are not necessarily launched because they are essential, but often because they are available for use, awaiting the identification of a problem that they can solve. Therefore, innovation can manifest itself by finding improved ways to apply existing technologies in design, making the product

or service perceived as innovative by the consumer (MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015, NOGAMI, VELOSO, 2017).

Currently, design plays a fundamental role in organizations, acting as a multifunctional catalyst that integrates different departments, such as technology, marketing, management and strategy. It aligns your goals and agendas, creating a common foundation between them. Despite the advancement of new technologies, unconventional professionals, such as designers, have the power to generate ideas at all stages of the innovation process, becoming an essential and organic part of the design process (CASTRO, 2011, VEIGA, VEIGA, et al., 2012).

3 Innovation Management

Regarding innovation management, regardless of the author, there is consensus on some essential fundamentals. They all highlight the importance of integrating technology, understanding consumer needs and creating meaning for the products or services developed. Furthermore, the management of design innovation also depends on the technology life cycle in the industry and the company's technology portfolio, directly influencing the innovation process (MEDEIROS, VIEIRA, et al., 2013, SILVA, DACORSO, 2013).

Finally, there are two distinct approaches to innovation, as observed by experts. One is driven by need (Need Pull), where market demands and needs drive innovation. The other is technology-driven (Technology Push), in which existing technology is explored and applied to create innovative solutions. Both approaches are vital in the context of design innovation, contributing to the creation of significant and impactful products and services (GATTI JUNIOR, YU, 2017, MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015).

There are two main approaches to innovation. In the first, called “need-driven”, innovation is guided by the demands already existing in the market. In this scenario, the need itself drives the innovation process. On the other hand, in the “technology-driven” approach, design uses already available technologies to create products or services. Both of these factors are crucial to progress. In some situations, technology drives development, especially in consumer-facing industries and more mature sectors. However, in more consumer-centric companies, it is often market demands that drive technology forward. In short, these two forces are in constant interaction and continuously influence innovation (MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015, SANCHES, MACHADO, 2014).

The technological dimension of innovation in two forms. The first, called “technology-push”, occurs when innovation is driven by a radical change in technology. The second, known

as “market-pull”, has as its starting point the observation of consumer needs, without necessarily depending on significant technological advances (GATTI JUNIOR, YU, 2017, MACEDO, MIGUEL, et al., 2015).

In addition to these perspectives, different starting points for the innovation process. These are established in advance by the designer during the conception of a product or service and shape the results perceived in the final delivery. There are three main categories of starting points:

- Trigger by technology: This includes process technology, taking advantage of different methods, and product technology, where specific product characteristics are established in advance, such as durability, strength or performance.
- Trigger by mode of use: This starting point is driven by the technical requirements and sensory and cognitive abilities of the users. The solution is designed considering the interaction between the product and the user.
- Trigger by shape: Primarily relevant to aesthetically appealing products, this starting point is highly subjective. It involves choosing shapes that best suit the product, allowing the designer significant creative freedom.

In summary, establishing the starting points for effective innovation management requires a deep understanding of the project and market context, both present and future. Additionally, it requires careful analysis to determine which processes and methods would be best suited for each specific project.

4 MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study is part of a literature study that examines significant gaps in the home appliance market. The mobility difficulties associated with refrigerators, stoves and washing machines have been a persistent challenge for those responsible for homes, directly impacting the effective cleaning of these appliances and the spaces around them. Through this bibliographical study, it is intended not only to identify existing gaps, but also to bring concrete proposals to address these issues and provide an overview of market demands and technological innovations necessary to overcome the challenges faced by local consumers.

4.1 Resources considered during the project:

High Strength Wheels: Equipped with sturdy and durable wheels, it glides smoothly on any surface, making moving a simple and effortless process.

- 1) Intelligent Locking System: Ensuring stability, the intelligent locking system ensures that your refrigerator remains safe and stable during cleaning or maintenance.
- 2) Ergonomic Design: Ergonomic design and easy to handle. Its height is carefully adjusted to facilitate cleaning under and behind the appliance.
- 3) Universal Compatibility: Designed to fit a wide variety of refrigerators, our innovation is compatible with most popular models on the market.

Figure 1 – Product test model

Source: SolidWorks (authors), 2023

The innovation will feature a lever at its base, meticulously designed to provide smooth and effective lifting of the equipment being supported. Furthermore, it will be equipped with a locking system on the wheel bearings, ensuring complete immobility and preventing any involuntary movement. The dimensions of this product will be customizable, adapting to different types of equipment, taking into account their specificities.

The importance of this innovation lies in its ability to solve a recurring problem. Many household appliances that are equipped with wheels end up facing the inconvenience of locking over time. This situation is aggravated by the fact that, given its location at the base of the equipment, lifting becomes an impossible task. By incorporating the lever and locking system, our product not only solves this problem, but raises the level of functionality and practicality, providing a long-lasting and efficient solution to this common issue in the daily use of wheeled equipment.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The difficulty of moving large appliances represents a significant challenge for many homes as it can complicate routine tasks such as cleaning and rearranging spaces, as well as being a constant source of frustration for users. Previously, the crucial importance of an innovation that facilitates the movement of these devices and that also simplifies cleaning and maintenance tasks related to them was highlighted.

This proposal incorporates a lever and an intelligent locking system on the wheels, ensuring smooth lifting and preventing involuntary movements during transport. Furthermore, the ability to customize the product's dimensions makes it adaptable to different equipment, taking into account the individual specificities of each device.

It should be noted that this innovation will have a profound impact on daily household activities: by eliminating the stress associated with transporting heavy household appliances, the aforementioned solution will provide a more efficient and accessible experience for users. Consumers are expected to not only benefit from improved mobility, but from simplified cleaning and maintenance tasks. The guaranteed stability of the locking system ensures safety during use, eliminates concerns about accidental movement, and gives users confidence.

Ultimately, this innovation aims to be designed to transform not only the functionality of home appliances, but also the overall experience of users in their homes, creating a more efficient, safe and convenient environment: expected to see a notable reduction in the physical effort required to the transport of heavy household appliances with the implementation of this innovation. This result alleviates the physical burden on consumers, and translates into a safer experience, significantly reducing the number of injuries related to movement, demonstrating that innovation can not only simplify the process, but also prevent damage to the physical integrity of users. Furthermore, there is an expectation of preservation of the appliances themselves: by reducing the risk of damage during transport, this innovative solution not only extends the useful life of appliances, but also saves resources for consumers, as the need for frequent repairs or replacements is considerably reduced.

In view of the above, it can be concluded that investing in innovative solutions to facilitate the transport of extremely heavy household appliances can have a profoundly positive impact on consumers' quality of life. In addition to alleviating the physical burden, innovation contributes to user safety, promotes the preservation of devices and boosts the efficiency of domestic activities. This study emphasizes the continued importance of technological development in the home appliance industry, demonstrating that carefully designed innovations

not only improve convenience for users, but promote the long-term health and well-being of consumers.

6 CONCLUSION

In the domestic scenario, the difficulty of moving large appliances has been a persistent issue, complicating routine activities such as cleaning and rearranging spaces. This problem has raised crucial questions about the need for innovations that not only facilitate the mobility of these devices, but also simplify the cleaning and maintenance tasks related to them.

The objective of the work was to develop an innovative solution to face this challenge. We introduced a proposal that incorporates an intelligent lever and a wheel locking system, providing smooth lifting and preventing involuntary movements during the transport of household appliances. Customizing the product's dimensions was also fundamental, allowing it to be adapted to different types of equipment.

Despite the advances achieved, there are opportunities for future research. Firstly, it is essential to implement and test this innovation in real-world situations to verify its effectiveness and usefulness. Furthermore, exploring methods to integrate assistive technologies such as sensors and remote control could further expand the functionality of these devices, making them more accessible, inclusive and intuitive for users.

Considering the growing interest in innovative and sustainable home solutions, investigating environmentally friendly materials for manufacturing these devices could be a promising area for future research. Furthermore, analyzing the socioeconomic impact of these innovations on homes, including the potential time and energy savings for users, would be valuable to better understand their value in everyday life.

Ultimately, this study provided a solid foundation for future investigations into home appliance mobility. By continuing to explore and improve these solutions, we can not only make people's lives easier, but also create a positive impact on their home experiences, turning challenges into innovative opportunities.

7 REFERENCES

Almodóvar, P., & Nguyen, Q.T. (2022). Product innovation of domestic firms versus foreign MNE subsidiaries: The role of external knowledge sources. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 184, 122000.

Bos-Brouwers, H. E. J. (2010). Corporate sustainability and innovation in SMEs: Evidence of themes and activities in practice. *Business strategy and the environment*, 19(7), 417-435.

Castro, BHR (2011). Influence of the structuring of R&D departments on innovation: a study in the agricultural machinery and implements industry in Brazil. *RAI Journal of Administration and Innovation*, 8(1), 196-220.

da Costa Nogami, VK, & Veloso, AR (2017). Disruptive innovation in low-income contexts: challenges and state-of-the-art national research in marketing. *RAI Journal of Administration and Innovation*, 14(2), 162-167.

da Veiga, CRP, da Veiga, CP, Del Corso, JM, & da Silva, WV (2012). The dynamics of technological innovation: the role of Demand Pull, Technology Push and Government Incentives in the Brazilian pharmaceutical industry. *REGE-Revista de Gestão*, 19(4), 515-534.

Gatti Junior, W., & Yu, A. (2017). Knowledge transformation in the innovation process: a multiple case study of developing the flex fuel technology in Brazil. *REGE-REVISTA DE MANAGEMENT*, 24(3), 256-267.

Macedo, MA, Miguel, PAC, & Casarotto Filho, N. (2015). The characterization of design thinking as an innovation model. *Revista de Administração e Inovação*, 12(3), 157-182.

Medeiros, J., Vieira, FGD, & da Costa Nogami, VK (2013). Market practices and innovation: forgotten dimensions. *RAI Journal of Administration and Innovation*, 10(2), 238-261.

Han, C., & Zhang, S. (2021). Multiple strategic orientations and strategic flexibility in product innovation. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 27(1), 100136.

Reimann, M., Xiong, Y., & Zhou, Y. (2019). Managing a closed-loop supply chain with process innovation for remanufacturing. *European Journal of Operational Research*, 276(2), 510-518.

Serrano-Garcia, J., Bikfalvi, A., Llach, J., & Arbelaez-Toro, J. J. (2021). Orchestrating capabilities, organizational dimensions and determinants in the pursuit of green product innovation. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 313, 127873.

Silva, G., & Dacorso, ALR (2013). Open innovation as a competitive advantage for micro and small companies. *RAI Journal of Administration and Innovation*, 10(3), 251-269.

Young, G. O. 1964. "Synthetic structure of industrial plastics (Book style with paper title and editor)," in *Plastics*, 2nd ed. vol. 3, J. Peters, Ed. New York: McGraw-Hill, 1964, pp. 15-64.